

References for database on variability (coefficient of variation: COV) of core strength, rebound number, and ultrasonic pulse velocity from existing concrete structures

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19391047>

The collected data references included 109 articles (Scanlon and Mikhailovsky 1987; Al-Mandil and Ziraba 1990; Qazweeni and Daoud 1991; Ward and Langan 1994; Shimuzu et al. 2000; Dias and Jayanandana 2003; Ackay 2004; Gennari-Santori 2005; Bhaskar et al. 2006; Rao et al. 2006; Dilek 2007; Rens and Kim 2007; Masi and Vona 2009; Monteiro and Goncalves 2009; Garnier et al. 2011; Shariati et al. 2011; Bilgehan 2011; Soustos et al. 2012; Hannachi and Gueteche 2012; Shang et al. 2012; Borosnyoi and Szilagyi 2013; Brencich et al. 2013; Hellebois et al. 2013; Masi and Chiauzzi 2013; Sena-Cruz et al. 2013; Pape and Melchers 2013; Nguyen et al. 2013; Nobile and Bonagura 2013; Giannini et al. 2014; Tirpude et al. 2014; Unanwa and Mahan 2014; Masi et al. 2014; Ondrej et al. 2014; Alwash et al. 2015; Nobile 2015; Sadzevicius et al. 2015; Pucinotti 2015; Borosnyói 2015; Gibas et al. 2015; Gomez-Cardenas et al. 2015; Breccolotti and Bonfigli 2015; Papworth et al. 2015; Gehlot et al. 2016; Noufid and Belattar 2016; Araki 2016; Peter et al. 2016; Pereira and Romao 2016; Masi et al. 2016; Ali-Benyahia et al. 2017; Cristofaro et al. 2017; Adnan 2017; Chatterjee et al. 2017; Venkatesh and Alapati 2017; Breccolotti et al. 2018; Uva et al. 2018; Dauji and Bhargava 2018; Gao et al. 2018; Kog 2018; Thomas and Ede 2018; Kocab et al. 2019; Rai et al. 2019; Ali-Benyahia et al. 2019; Dauji et al. 2019a; Dauji et al. 2019b; Choudhury et al. 2019; Ambroziak et al. 2019; Masi et al. 2019; Rymes et al. 2019; Qasrawi 2019; Kog 2019; Ogunbayo and Aigbavboa 2019; Ogunbayo et al. 2019; Lasisi et al. 2019; Araki 2020; Santini et al. 2020; Dey et al. 2020; Wang et al. 2020; Zaborac et al. 2020; Indian Railways 2020; Siorikis et al. 2020; Brencich et al.

2020; Cristofaro et al. 2020; Craeye et al. 2020; Bolberea et al. 2021; Raut et al. 2021; Karmakar et al. 2021; Alrasyid and Sutrisno 2021; Ambroziak and Malinowski 2021; Ambroziak et al. 2021; Kondalkar et al. 2021; Masi et al. 2021; Kumar et al. 2021; Ngo et al. 2021; Bonagura and Nobile 2021; Vona 2022; Diaferio and Varona 2022; Faroz et al. 2022; Karatosun et al. 2022; Dauji and Karmakar 2022; Dauji 2023a; Ali-Benyahia et al. 2023; Abbas et al. 2023; Bhargava et al. 2023; Boussahoua et al. 2023; Herki et al. 2023; Oroza and Ricardo 2023; Pang et al. 2023; Gebauer et al. 2023; Arora et al. 2024), some of which were based on common datasets.

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